

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON SANKRAMAK ROGA MENTIONED IN AYURVEDIC LITERATURE

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ABSTARCT

Prevention is the wise way to avoid incidence of diseases. In today's era various amount of communicable diseases are seen to be in increasing amount, the prevalence rate has seen increasing while mortality rates are decreasing, communicable diseases still contribute significantly to the overall disease burden in the country. In Ayurveda Sankramaka roga has been explained which can correlate to communicable diseases which mainly occurs due to microorganism invasion. In literature of Ayurveda like Charak Samhita described concept of Janapadodhwansa (mass destruction) due to vitiated state of vayu, jal, doshas and dhatu, which resembles Pandemic of modern science. This article gives brief information about ayurvedic view on Sankramak Roga and their management.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Sankramaka roga, Janapadodhwansa, Aupsargik Roga, Agantuja vyadhi, Communicable diseases, Infectious diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Communicable diseases can be associated with Sankramaka Roga and Aupsargik Roga terminologies in Ayurveda. Classical texts of Ayurveda mentioned various references related to infectious diseases, their treatments, ways of prevention. As per Ayurveda, the pandemic situation can be considered as Janapadodhwansa caused by Dushita vayu(Air), jal(Water), kal(Time) and desh(Region). Various means of transmission of Sankramak Roga are

mentioned as prasanngat, gatra sansparshat, sahbhojanat, sahshayya, etc means these diseases can transmit from one another through physical, chemical and biological means. As per Ayurveda the current pandemic problem can be considered as an Agantuja vyadhi. Agantuja vyadhi can spread from one person to another and when large population gets affected then these diseases turned to Janapadodhwamsa.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To review the basic principles of Sankramak rogas described in various text of Ayurveda.
2. To Study the Nidan of Sankramak Roga described in various text of Ayurveda.
3. To study the concept of Communicable Disease & its causes.
4. To compare the principal of the Sankramaka Roga with special reference to Communicable Disease.
5. To review the Sankramaka Roga with respect to Communicable Diseases in present scenario for its preventions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Literary review on Sankramaka Roga have been collected from different Ayurvedic classical text i.e. Charak, Sushrut and Vagbhat Samhita.
2. Literary review on communicable diseases has been collected from different modern texts and from various research papers, journals, articles and internet.
3. After the collection & selection of the matter have been summaries.

4. All the matter have been making fruitful & useful according to present needs of forthcoming Scholar.

Concepts about Janapadodhwans

The disease or ailment and their causes are same in most of the ancient texts^[1],

INFECTIOUS DISEASES ACCORDING TO CHARAK SAMHITA

In charak samhita vimansthan adhyay 3rd when agnivesh ask why people having different prakruti, age, ahar, bal, agni still got diseased which destructs population in particular area. It is similar with pandemic of modern terminology. Answerd by bhagvan atreya as people can have different Prakruti & Aahara but factors like Vayu & Desha are common and vitiation of these factors leads to the production of Roga which termed as Janapadodhwans. Common factors causing epidemic are Dushita vayu(Air), jal(Water), kal(Time) and desh(Region). In janapadodhwansaniyam adhay of charak vimansthan characteristic's features of polluted air, water, place and time had given.^[2] According to Charaka Adharma is the root cause of Janapadodhwans along with awful conduction of Dincharya and Ritucharya.^[3] Charaka believe that accumulation of causative factors like; vitiated Doshas, Dushyas along with depleted Bala enhance susceptibility for the disease.^[4]

In viman sthan of charak samhita krimis have been described and considered as two types:- innate and disease causing /creepy krimis. The krimis described as tiny, having large number of legs and posseses different colours. Unhygienic living pattern may enhance prevalence of such krimis in our body.^[5]

Charak samhita not only mentioned unmad, apasmar, atisar and jwar but also elaborated infectious diseases along with their types. Sutra sthan chapter 18 mentioned shoth and described krimi bite as reason for agantuj shoth. charak samhita in 18/4 chapter states that swelling and inflammation confirm transitional presence of bacteria or other microbes.^[6]

Charak samhita viman chapter 3 described role of jal(water), vayu(air), desh(region) and kala(time) in relation to epidemic diseases and mentioned term Aapgat guna. The contamination / pollution through water and air produces various infectious diseases while specific environmental conditions associated with desh and kala affects mass population for certain period of time.^[7]

Charak chikista 30 adhyay explains vaginal diseases may occurs due to unhygienic condition of vaginal portion or due to use of contaminated water or through the infections caused by krimis.^[8]

Charak sutra sthan 17/8,9,10 encompasses description of uradvajatrugna vyadhi, here it was mentioned that dust smoke cold and sunlight are some major reasons for infections in head region. Characteristics of krimi which causes shiroroga also described and it was stated that krimis in head region produces diseases symptoms, in this regard krimij and sannipataj both types of disorders termed as infectious disorders.^[9]

Charak sutra sthan 17/37-38 mentioned that heart of hypersensitive person may affected by krimis which produced through kled, initially they produces in a particular region of heart then gradually affecting whole body.^[10]

In nidan sthan adhyay chapter 8/22 apasmar the reason of aagantuj apasmar is similar to unmad, here jwara and rajyashma were considered as infectious diseases here diseases are described which occur due to presence of other disease in the situation of vyadhi sankar when disease occurs due to the secondary infection.^[11]

With reference to trushna roga, charak samhita (charak chikista sthan 22/7) considered trushna roga as aopsargik roga and described it is as a painful and harmful diseases considered trushna as updrav of visarproga.^[12] Also acharya sushrut has considered word aopsargik as upasragaj as like infectious.^[13]

In charak chikista sthan 23 ailments related to poisonous infections are described with description of poisonous organisms^[14] and their management.^[15] This chapter encompasses information related to signs, symptoms and diseases caused by mushak^[16], luta,^[17] dogs and poisonous flies.^[18]

25th chapter of charak chikistasthan vrana chikista mentioned agantuj vrana and infectious diseases caused by krimi.^[19] Similarly in chapter, 24 vranadosh it was mentioned that microorganisms and krimis may causes wounds on skin, ligaments and veins.^[20]

Trimarmiya adhyay explains diseases of shir, hriday, basti where krimij hriday roga^[21] and krimij shir roga were considered as diseases of hriday and shir caused by krimi. Similarly

bad smell in ear and eye infections also mentioned diseases caused by krimis and termed as jeerna pratishay, peenas, apeenas, dushtipratishya and peenas.^[22]

Charak sutrasthan chapter 6 mentioned hansodak as the natural method of disinfection to prevent microbial infections.^[23] In chapter 7 krimis were mentioned as a cause of aagantuj disease, here bhuta indicates bacterial infection.^[24] Similarly kshya and causes of kshay are also mentioned in charak sutra sthan 17/77 which somewhere quotes about infectious diseases further elaborates sub- bacterial infections and other infections which may cause kshay, here prevalence of kshay of ashtbindu oaj considered as lethal.^[25]

In vidhradhi chapter reasons of internal vidhradhi were described such as sanklistha, virudh and dushta bhojan. In this regards the krimi was considered as one of the reason for yakrit vidhradhi.

In 26th chapter of charak sutrasthan, virudha ahar concept has been mentioned, where 18 types of virudha aahar have been described including, pak virudha, kostha virudha, parihaar virudha, upchar virudha and vidhi virudha which have also been considered as the cause of infectious disease which may occurs due to the virudha aahar such as: aandhapan, jalodar, pandu, visuchika, kilas, kustha, grahdhu, shoth, jwar and peenas.^[26]

In chikista sthan of charak chapter 13, consumption of dirty and unhygienic foods and vegetable may lead development of abdominal diseases is mentioned in samnya samprapti of udar roga.^[27]

In chapter 7 of chikistasthan, charakacharya mentioned treatment of kustha where term virudha aanpan was cause of kustha. Virudha aanpan means consumption of bad quality food and water which infected by various means. Intake of such types of food materials may not only lead kustha but also causes disorders such as : twachagat and strotogat. This concept of aanpan not only implies to kustha but also to the charakokt epidemic concept of virudh aanpan. The basic concept of virudh aanpan associated with pranahvah strotas, aanpan strotas, rasvaha strotas, mutravah strotas, malvah strotas, raktavah strotas and mansvah strotas.^[28]

In chapter 3rd of vimansthan, bhagwan atreya has answered to questions of agnivesh that the reason behind dushit vayu, jal kal, desh are mainly the adharmas or the sins done in previous life, which means pradnyaparadha is the root cause behind Janapadodhwans, along with shatraprabhav, rakshoganadi and abhishap.^[29]

INFECTIOUS DISEASES ACCORDING TO SUSHRUTA SAMHITA

Acharya Sushrut not only discussed infectious diseases but also mentioned types of infection and their mode of transmission:-

According to Sushruta Samhita Nidansthan Adhyaya, Acharya Sushruta has mentioned Aupasargik rogas in Kushthanidan. They are contagious diseases and Prasnaga, Gatra Sansparsha, eating & sleeping together, sexual contact; sharing clothes and ornaments, etc. can be considered as mode of transmission for such diseases. Kustha, Jwara, Shosha and Netrabhishyanda are considered as Aupasargik rogas which spread from person to person.^[30]

Sushrut samhita described sankramak as aupsargik roga and stated that sexual intercourse, physical contact, air contamination, eating, sleeping and sharing objects with infected person may transmit contagious disease from one person to another. In this regards leprosy, fevers, tuberculosis, conjunctivitis and some other diseases were considered as diseases to be transmitted from one person to another. In this statement aacharya mentioned Kustha and other infectious diseases which are directly or indirectly associated with infections.^[31]

It is believed that term prasangat referes with yona prasang since infections diseases may transmit by infectious person to other.

Gatra prasanga described as contact with the body of an infected person may be through sexual intercourse or by other ways. These aopsargik diseases may get transmitted from one to another and current scenario of life style enhances such types of contact thus life style need to modify in such a way so that chances of gatra prasanga reduced.

Nihshwasat indicates infectious diseases which may occur due to the breathing through the respiratory system. Diseases occurs through the respiratory infections such as; jwara and masurika etc. Comes under the category of sankramaka roga they spread through swasa, kasa and pratishay.

Acharya clarified the spread of such infections by taking example of jwar and shosh. Eating food with infected person, sleeping together, sharing clothes and other objects also spreads infections from one to another.^[32]

Sushruta samhita also describes epidemic Sankraman as Janpadodhawans which harms the human body at a particular area. Similarly frequent touching of patient body, inhaling the infected air and sitting with diseased person may lead to diseases such as : kustha, jwara,

shosh, netrabhishyanda and another aupasargik roga which may spread from one person to another.^[33]

Aacharya sushrut has also mentioned Gramyadharam Sevan as causes of kustha. Mentioned in shlok 34-35 corresponding to prasangat kustha which may occur due to sexual intercourse with the person suffering from kustha.^[34]

In sutra sthan chapter 45 aacharya sushrut has mentioned water induced infectious diseases. Sutrasthan 45/8-9 mentioned that when a person comes in contact with insects, urine, debris of dead insects and infected water then one may suffers from external disease like boils and internal diseases like ajjerna and malavrodha.^[35]

Various kind of infectious diseases described by acharya sushrutra through various contexts as are congregated like following:-

Nidan sthan	chapter 7 th	-- sannipatik udar roga
	Chapter 12 th	-- updansh
	Chapter 13 th	- parivartika, nirudh prakas, ahiputna, mukhdushika, masurika, arunsika and arbud
	Chapter 16 th	- osthaprakop . Upkush, galshundika and tandukeri
Kalpasthan	chapter 7 th	- alarka visha
	chapter 20 th	-karnapak, putikarna, krimikarna, karnastrav etc
Uttartantra	Chapter 24 th	- pratishay, dushtpratishya
	Chapter 25 th	- krimij shiroroga
	Chapter 26 th	- krimi
	Chapter 61 th	-graha
	Chapter 28 th	- yonivyapad
	Chapter 40 th	- atisar
	Chapter 43 th	- krimij hriday roga

Various kind of infectious diseases described by acharya vagbhata through various contexts as are congregated like following:-

In nidan sthan chapter 12th udar roga^[36], in chapter 13th-shoth are explained.^[37]

In uttarsthan chapter 6th - bhutounmad^[38], chapter 15th - netra roga^[39], in chapter 19th - nasa roga^[40], dustha pratishay, pakva pratishay and apeenas^[41], mukha roga^[42] and danta roga^[43] are explained.

In chapter 23th of uttarsthan shiroroga nad krimis are mentioned.^[44]

Chapter 38th explains mushak, aaku and alerk visha.^[45]

ACCORDING TO LAGHUTRAYI

Aachrya Madhavkar has mentioned the classification of infectious diseases and their modes of transmission along with detailed description of infectious disease. Similarly Aacharya Bhavprakash has mentioned some other infectious diseases in his classical text. He classified these diseases under the category of Kuprasangaj. So we can say that Ayurveda literature encompasses useful information related to infectious diseases. Ayurveda text provides knowledge about the types of microbes, their sources. And mode of transmission and management of disease caused by such microbes. Therefore it is required to correlates folklore concepts of infectious disease with modern perspective to enhance understating of traditional knowledge regarding microbial infections.^[46]

CONCLUSION

Sankramak Roga, as explained in Ayurveda, constitutes a significant group of communicable diseases that adversely impact individual health and community well-being, while also creating an economic burden. These diseases may spread through direct contact or indirectly via contaminated air, water, objects, and other environmental factors. Modern medicine has contributed various therapeutic options, yet concerns like drug resistance and adverse reactions limit their sustainable effectiveness. Ayurveda emphasizes that the most effective strategy lies in **prevention, immunity enhancement (Bala Vriddhi), and maintenance of Dosh equilibrium**, rather than relying solely on curative interventions.

Classical Ayurvedic texts explain that diminished Dhatus, altered body temperature, lowered immunity, and Doshic vitiation increase susceptibility to microbial invasion, leading to conditions such as Kustha, Jwara, Shosha, and Netrabhishyanda. Furthermore, Acharya Charaka describes the pivotal role of air (Vayu), water (Udaka), habitat (Desha), and seasonal variations (Kala) in the emergence and spread of Aupsargika Rogas, often culminating in epidemic outbreaks (Janapadodhwansa).

In this context, **Dinacharya (daily regimen)**, **Rutucharya (seasonal regimen)**, **Sadvritta Palana (ethical and behavioral discipline)**, and **Achara Rasayana (code of conduct for mental and social well-being)** play a central role in strengthening immunity, maintaining internal balance, and protecting the body from communicable diseases. By promoting healthy lifestyle practices, enhancing psychosocial stability, and encouraging harmony with natural cycles, these regimens form a comprehensive preventive framework against Sankramak Roga.

Thus, Ayurveda not only explains the pathogenesis of communicable diseases through Doshic imbalance and microbial factors but also offers a holistic preventive approach. Incorporating **lifestyle discipline, seasonal adaptation, ethical conduct, and immune-strengthening measures** ensures better disease resistance at both individual and community levels, thereby providing sustainable strategies to combat Sankramak Roga.

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